

1 *REGULAR PAPER*

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3 **Optimization of forest sampling strategies for woody**
4 **plant species distribution modelling at the landscape**
5 **scale**

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19 **ABSTRACT**

20 Forest management increasingly needs the support of species distribution models
21 (SDMs). However, different challenges remain to be addressed before the practical
22 use and generalization of these models in the design of management measures in
23 forest ecosystems. Due to the limited resources that are typically available for forest
24 management, including the forest inventory phase, it is necessary to optimize the
25 sampling approaches. Opportunistic sampling may be one strategy to reduce sampling
26 costs, but the accuracy and suitability of the assessments derived from this sampling
27 remain yet poorly addressed, particularly in forest landscapes. On the other hand,
28 different forestry applications require landscape-wide estimates but still with fine
29 resolution (ideally meters) as to guide management interventions. We, here, assess in
30 detail the performance of the classical regular (systematic) sampling strategy and
31 three different opportunistic samplings approaches along roads and tracks in a forest-
32 dominated Biosphere Reserve ($\approx 15,000$ ha) in central Spain. We use specifically
33 gathered field data in different inventories with sampling intensities of about 1-2
34 plots/km². We compare, for each sampling strategy, the resultant consensus species
35 distribution models for 28 woody plant species (trees and shrubs) developed at a
36 spatial resolution of 25 m. We found that SDMs were reliable ($AUC > 0.75$) for 20
37 species out of 28 using either an opportunistic or/and systematic sampling. In general,
38 opportunistic sampling was more efficient than systematic sampling, resulting in
39 SDMs with a comparable accuracy for a lower inventory cost or in more accurate
40 SDMs for the same sampling effort. This was mainly because the four sampling
41 strategies adequately captured the environmental variability of the study area, and
42 because plots in the opportunistic sampling were located at a sufficient distance from
43 tracks to avoid potential edge effects. The minimum sample size and the species
44 ecology should, however, be evaluated with caution in each case. We conclude that
45 opportunistic sampling along tracks may be a practical and cost-effective option for
46 SDMs in forest landscapes, as long as the density and spatial arrangement of tracks

47 are sufficient to cover the full range of environmental conditions. This prerequisite
48 could be evaluated, before the inventory phase, using available statistical approaches
49 and spatial layers, potentially allowing for a remarkable saving of sampling resources
50 in forest management planning. Species distribution models calibrated at the
51 landscape extent with fine resolution could hence become ever more powerful and
52 cost-effective tools for forest management and planning in both planted and natural
53 forests.

54

55 *Keywords:* ecological modelling; forest landscapes; forest management tools;
56 sampling resource optimization; sampling design; forest inventory.

57

58 *Abbreviations:*

59 SDMs: species distribution models

60 **1. Introduction**

61

62 Species distribution models (SDMs) are powerful methods in forest management
63 and plant species ecology research (Henderson *et al.*, 2014). Primarily, they can
64 deliver potential species distribution and vegetation maps at different scales (Guisan
65 *et al.*, 2017), which are essential in forest management and conservation planning.
66 SDMs support the understanding, for example, of plant biodiversity patterns (Mateo
67 *et al.*, 2016; D'Amen *et al.*, 2017), potential effects of invasive plant species
68 (Petitpierre *et al.*, 2012; Mateo *et al.*, 2015) and invasive forest pathogens (Václavík
69 *et al.*, 2010), climate change effects on plant species (Thuiller *et al.*, 2008; Engler *et*
70 *al.*, 2011) and forest distribution (Moreno-Fernández *et al.*, 2016; van der Maaten *et*
71 *al.*, 2017), endangered species management (Rovzar *et al.*, 2016), ecological forest
72 restoration (Gastón *et al.*, 2014), etc.

73 Different methodological aspects can affect the performance of these models
74 (Guisan and Zimmermann, 2000; Mateo *et al.*, 2011), such as the minimum sample
75 size required (Wisz *et al.*, 2008; Mateo *et al.*, 2010b), parameterization (Moreno-
76 Amat *et al.*, 2015), or pseudo-absences generation (Wisz and Guisan, 2009; Mateo *et*
77 *al.*, 2015). Significant advances have been made in the last years on those
78 methodological questions (Guisan *et al.*, 2017). However, two of these essential
79 topics need more exploration before the application of these models in forest
80 management can be generalized. First, SDMs are usually fitted on data achieved
81 through sampling strategies not expressly planned for modelling (Loiselle *et al.*,
82 2008) or management goals (opportunistic data). On the other hand, classical forest
83 inventories are commonly done through regular-systematic sampling strategies (Mello
84 *et al.*, 2015). Are SDMs developed with opportunistic or systematic sampled data
85 comparable and reliable for forest management purposes? Second, the bulk of SDMs
86 studies are defined over large areas (regional and continental extent) with a coarse
87 resolution (1-50 km). This is still far from the use of SDMs at the landscape extent
88 and fine grain resolution (meters), which is required to support forest management

89 interventions (Gastón and García-Viñas, 2010). Indeed, numerous forestry
90 applications rely on the correct evaluation of models developed at the landscape scale,
91 such as the selection of species for reforestation (Gastón *et al.*, 2014); accurate
92 evaluation of climate change effects (Randin *et al.*, 2009); management of plant
93 diversity patterns (Dubuis *et al.*, 2011) and endangered species (Rovzar *et al.*, 2016).

94 Databases derived from opportunistic sampling strategies (Graham *et al.*, 2004;
95 Brotons *et al.*, 2007) are classically achieved from natural history collections (Araújo
96 and Williams, 2000). These databases have several benefits: quantity, accessibility,
97 and extensive geographic and temporal scales (Garcillán and Ezcurra, 2011).
98 Conversely, the primary constraint of these databases is that they do not derive from
99 specific prearranged samplings. The data are usually surveyed near tracks or attractive
100 botanical zones (Schulman *et al.*, 2007). Consequently, opportunistic databases are
101 low-cost; nevertheless they could be spatially biased (Jones, 2011). For example, a
102 sampling strategy following tracks could be related to spatial bias, which can lead to
103 climatic or ecological bias (Hortal *et al.*, 2008), which in turn could affect the SDMs
104 performance (Hirzel and Guisan, 2002). However, it is also possible that a sampling
105 strategy following tracks adequately covers the study area (no spatial bias), thus
106 containing the climatic variability and the environmental conditions wholly. Different
107 authors (Kadmon *et al.*, 2004; Loiselle *et al.*, 2008) deal with this issue at coarse
108 resolutions and regional scale, and they concluded that it is achievable to obtain
109 reliable SDMs from opportunistic sampling strategies. Natural history collections are
110 also unlikely to have the spatial resolution and density of observations required to
111 conduct forest management and planning. Therefore, a more detailed sampling
112 strategy at the landscape scale should be defined to guide forestry applications.

113 Species distribution modelling aimed at small geographic regions and a fine
114 resolution was infrequently conducted until recently, but nowadays many research
115 teams are developing SDMs in small areas and fine resolutions (D'Amen *et al.*, 2015;
116 D'Amen *et al.*, 2017; Scherrer *et al.*, 2017). This is primarily because of the new
117 accessibility to high resolution (meters) GIS free data, such as digital elevation

118 models, forest maps, remote sensing or LIDAR images. Nevertheless, the factors
119 encompassed in species distribution modelling are not compatible among different
120 scales (Mateo *et al.*, 2017) and the results from previous methodological studies
121 conducted at larger areas and coarser resolutions (see above) might not be consistent
122 with this local scale and the related forestry applications. Therefore, before the
123 generalization of the application of landscape species distribution modelling to forest
124 and woodland management, additional methodological studies and insights are
125 needed.

126 Gathering data at local-landscape level is, however, inherently costly in time and
127 resources. Considering the limited resources that governments or management
128 agencies can usually allocate to implement forest and woodland management,
129 resources should be optimized when capturing the data in the field and during the
130 modelling process. In this regard, comparisons of opportunistic low-cost sampling
131 strategies with systematic (regular) sampling are needed. Systematic sampling has
132 been shown to be one of the most robust sampling procedures (Hirzel and Guisan,
133 2002), but the cost and time required for both sampling strategies are very different.
134 Here, we investigate and compare, for 28 woody species, the reliability of SDMs
135 obtained under two different sampling strategies at the landscape scale: systematic
136 (more resource demanding) and opportunistic along tracks and roads (less resource
137 demanding). Our initial hypothesis is that systematic sampling could be necessary to
138 more accurately reflect fine-scale species distributions in the forest landscape
139 (Edwards *et al.*, 2006; Braunisch and Suchant, 2010). However, we hypothesize too
140 that opportunistic sampling could derive reliable SDMs if the sampling intensity
141 (minimum sample size, Mateo *et al.*, 2010b) is appropriate, and if the accessible areas
142 by roads and tracks do not include significant spatial biases, so that they capture the
143 range of environmental conditions in the study area.

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146 **2. Materials and methods**

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148 *2.1. Study area*

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150 The study was developed at the *Sierra del Rincón* Biosphere Reserve (41°03'N
151 3°29'W, Central Spain). The extension of the area is 15,231 ha, elevation ranges from
152 670 to 2,200 m, mean temperature ranges from 4.9 to 13.2 °C, and rainfall ranges
153 from 650 to 1,300 mm/year. Soils are derived from siliceous substrates, mostly from
154 gneiss, schists, quartzites, and slates. A mosaic of forests, shrublands and grasslands
155 cover the Reserve. Forests are mainly dominated by oaks (*Quercus pyrenaica*) and
156 pines (*Pinus sylvestris*, *P. pinaster*, *P. nigra*), the latter as a consequence of the
157 afforestation programs of the 1950s. The Reserve includes the *Montejo* beech forest,
158 which is the SW distribution limit of *Fagus sylvatica*.

159

160 *2.2. Sampling strategies and distribution data*

161

162 We carried out and compared two different sampling strategies: (1) a systematic
163 sampling, and (2) an opportunistic sampling along tracks and roads. All sampling
164 plots were positioned precisely using a GPS, and presence/absence of all woody (trees
165 and shrubs) species was recorded at woodland (forest and shrublands) areas in
166 circular plots with a 10 m radius. Plots at pastures, inaccessible and non-natural
167 vegetation areas (rocks, crops, villages, etc.) were discarded. Finally, 28 woody
168 species (9 trees and 19 shrubs, see Appendix A) present in a minimum of 5 plots were
169 used for modelling. They represent typical genus of Mediterranean plant species, for
170 example: *Adenocarpus* sp., *Calluna* sp., *Cistus* sp., *Crataegus* sp., *Cytisus* sp., *Erica*
171 sp., *Fraxinus* sp., *Genista* sp., *Halimium* sp., *Helichrysum* sp., *Ilex* sp., *Juniperus* sp.,
172 *Lavandula* sp., *Pinus* sp., *Prunus* sp., *Quercus* sp., *Salix* sp., *Santolina* sp., *Sorbus* sp.,
173 *Thymus* sp.

174 The systematic sampling was designed *a priori* following the regular lattice over
175 the complete study area with vertices separated by 1000 m, coinciding with those of

176 the 4th Spanish National Forest Inventory. A total of 132 plots were sampled (Fig. 1a).
177 It was an exhaustive sampling routine that involved two persons performing fieldwork
178 for approximately seven weeks. This sampling strategy requires a more significant
179 time of displacement walking, in some cases through steep terrain, in order to arrive
180 at the plots than an opportunistic sampling.

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182

183 **Fig. 1.** Sampling strategies compared in this study: a) systematic sampling (132 plots regularly
184 sampled); b) opportunistic1 (302 plots sampled along road and tracks); c) opportunistic2 (139 plots
185 selected from previous one with a minimum distance of 700 m apart from each other), and d)
186 opportunistic3 (177 plots selected from opportunistic1 on roads and main trafficable tracks).

187

188 An opportunistic sampling along roads and tracks was achieved independently;
189 plots were established at 1000 m road or tracks intervals, and the starting point at
190 every road-track was set up at 500 m of the road-track sector. However, unlike
191 systematic sampling, the distance between plots could frequently be less than 1000 m
192 because of parallel roads or tracks, topography, or nearby sectors due to the road-track
193 path. A total of 302 circular plots (opportunistic1, Fig. 1b) were sampled. The plots
194 were situated at 20 m downhill distance from the roads or tracks to reduce any
195 potential edge effects or other direct consequences of human influence. This sampling
196 was considerably fewer resources demanding (two persons performing fieldwork for
197 approximately four weeks) than the systematic sampling approach (i.e., even though
198 it collected information on more than the double number of plots). In order to have a
199 similar number of plots to the systematic sampling, we selected from opportunistic
200 sampling (302 plots) the 139 plots that were a minimum of 700 m apart from each
201 other (opportunistic2, Fig. 1c). On the other hand, in order to evaluate the importance
202 of road-track network density, we selected the plots available from opportunistic1 on
203 roads and main trafficable tracks by any vehicle, thus excluding tracks only trafficable
204 by 4x4 cars, which resulted in 177 plots (opportunistic3, Fig. 1d).

205

206 2.3. *Environmental variables*

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208 Species and biodiversity spatial distribution patterns are driven by different
209 processes at different scales (McGill, 2010; Mateo et al., 2017). SDMs fitted at
210 landscape scale are expected to capture local conditions important for plants, e.g.
211 vegetation structure or landscape features, as microtopography. A set of twelve local
212 meaningful environmental (topography, vegetation structure and hydrography)
213 variables were generated: aspect, *northness* (orientation in the South-North axis),
214 *eastness* (orientation in the West-East axis), solar radiation in the summer solstice,
215 accumulated flow into each down-slope cell, least surface distance (m) to any stream,
216 compound topographic index, heat load index, tree canopy cover fraction derived

217 from a LIDAR image, elevation, slope, and curvature. To avoid multicollinearity, we
218 ran a correlation analysis between each pair of variables and we checked that the
219 Pearson's correlation coefficient was always less than 0.8, and six variables were
220 selected: 1) Distance to streams: for each pixel, we calculated the least surface
221 distance (m) to any stream (HEC-GeoHMS, Fleming and Doan, 2013). This variable
222 could be meaningful for hydrophilic plants. 2) Canopy cover above 3 m derived from
223 a LIDAR image (Centro Nacional de Información Geográfica,
224 <http://centrodedescargas.cnig.es/CentroDescargas/index.jsp>). It is the fraction of
225 ground area covered by the vertical projection of tree crown perimeters. It is an
226 indirect measure of the vegetation structure. 3) Heat load index (HLI): Southwest-
227 facing slope has warmer temperatures than a Southeast-facing one. The McCune and
228 Keon (2002) method accounts for this by "folding" the aspect. Additionally, this
229 method accounts for the steepness of the slope. It is a measure of the local topography
230 and an indirect measure of the temperature, and it is an important factor to model the
231 distribution of plants 4) Elevation: derived from a 25 m resolution digital elevation
232 model (DEM, Centro Nacional de Información Geográfica), it is a measure of the
233 topography and an indirect measure of the temperature. 5) Slope: derived from the
234 DEM. It is an indicator of the local topography and an indirect measure of the local
235 microclimatic conditions. 6): Aspect: orientation in degrees derived from the DEM. It
236 is an indicator of the local topography and an indirect measure of the local
237 microclimatic conditions. All the independent variables were generated at 25 m
238 resolution and projected at ETRS89 UTM 30N using ArcGIS 10.3 and R 3.3.2
239 software.

240

241 *2.4. Species distribution modelling*

242

243 Different species distribution modelling techniques offer different results and
244 performance (Elith *et al.*, 2006; Mateo *et al.*, 2010a). However, the use of an
245 ensemble (consensus) model of various modelling techniques significantly increases

246 the accuracy of predictions (Araújo and New, 2007; Marmion *et al.*, 2009). Here, for
247 28 woody species (Appendix A) and four sampling strategies (systematic,
248 opportunistic1, opportunistic2 and opportunistic3), we ran consensus models on the
249 basis of the results of three different techniques: generalized linear models (GLM;
250 McCullagh and Nelder, 1989), boosted regression trees (BRT; Friedman, 2001), and
251 random forests (RF; Breiman, 2001). Default parameters were used for the three
252 techniques. The assembling of the models was carried out for three different
253 modelling approaches (see Appendix B) in order to optimize the parameterization for
254 species with a low sample size (Mateo *et al.*, 2010b). After comparing their
255 performance, here we will include only the results of the modelling approach that
256 offered the best results (see Appendix B for more details, approach2). In this
257 approach, the performance of the models was assessed by randomly splitting ten times
258 (replicates models) the data into an 80% dataset to generate the models and a 20%
259 dataset to estimate their predictive accuracy (verification); so we produced a total of
260 30 models per species and sampling strategy. After elimination of all models with an
261 $AUC < 0.5$ (not different or worse than random), we generated for each species and
262 sampling strategy a consensus model, consisting of a weighted mean of the model's
263 predictions, where the contribution of each model was proportional to its predictive
264 accuracy (AUC). We used a ratio of 1.3 between a weight and the following or prior
265 one ($prob.mean.weight.decay = 1.3$ in the function `BIOMOD_EnsembleModeling` of
266 `biomod2` package). All the models were generated using `biomod2` (Thuiller *et al.*,
267 2009) R package (R Development Core Team). The relative importance of each
268 independent variable was calculated by a repeated random permutation test (Thuiller
269 *et al.*, 2009). First, we calculated the mean value (10 replicates models) for each
270 species, sampling strategy, variable, and modelling method (GLM, BRT, and RF).
271 Finally, we calculated the average for each species, sampling strategy, and variable.

272

273 *2.5. Model comparison and evaluation*

274

275 We compared the four obtained consensus models (systematic, opportunistic1,
276 opportunistic2 and opportunistic3) for each species using the Pearson's correlation
277 coefficient. It was calculated by comparison of the three opportunistic consensus
278 models with the systematic consensus model.

279 The area under the ROC curve (AUC) statistics was calculated with the training
280 data used to run the models (verification) and also with independent data (evaluation).
281 For the independent assessment, we employed data from the opposite sampling
282 strategy as follows. Opportunistic1, opportunistic2, and opportunistic3 consensus
283 models were evaluated with all the plots from the systematic sampling strategy (132
284 plots). Systematic consensus models were assessed with the plots from the
285 opportunistic2 sampling strategy (139 plots) in order to have a comparable number of
286 plots.

287 In order to quantify the effect of sampling strategy on models' predictive
288 accuracy leaving aside inter-species effect, a mixed-model regression was fitted for
289 the 112 AUCs values (4 consensus models for each of the 28 analyzed species)
290 assessed for models' evaluation (independent data). Within this model, the *Sampling*
291 *strategy* was handled as a fixed factor with four levels (systematic, opportunistic1,
292 opportunistic2 and opportunistic3), whereas *Species* was considered as a random one
293 in order to correctly account for species repeated measurements effect, namely:
294 $AUC_{ijk} = \beta_0 + SS_j + \delta_i + e_{ij}$, where: AUC_{ij} is the estimated AUC for the model of
295 the species 'i' with the sampling strategy 'j'; β_0 is the intercept and matches the mean
296 AUC of the reference group (systematic sampling); SS_j is the effect of the sampling
297 strategy 'j' over the mean AUC of the reference group ($SS = 0$ when j= systematic
298 sampling); δ_i is the random effect of the species 'i'; and e_{ij} is the error term. Model fit
299 was assessed according to the procedure by Zuur *et al.* (2009).

300

301 2.6. Environmental variability

302

303 We hypothesized that reliable SDMs could be obtained using an opportunistic
304 sampling strategy if most of the environmental variability was effectively captured in
305 the sample. Here, we propose two straightforward analyses to evaluate this
306 hypothesis. These explorations could be run before the fieldwork is done, allowing to
307 assess if an opportunistic sampling is appropriate or not in a given study area. First,
308 we sampled randomly the value of the six environmental variables at 10,000
309 background pixels (assumed to represent the full set of environmental conditions in
310 the study area), and at the plots of the four sampling strategies (systematic,
311 opportunistic1, opportunistic2 and opportunistic3). These data were employed in two
312 different explorative analyses: boxplot and principal component analysis (PCA). The
313 first option is an univariate analysis; we simply represented the data of the four
314 sampling strategies and the background in a different boxplot for each of the six
315 environmental variables. The second option is a multivariate analysis: a PCA of the
316 environmental variables recorded at each background point was performed to identify
317 the combinations of variables that best summarized the environmental variability in
318 the study area. The first two PCA axes jointly accounted for about 70% of the total
319 environmental variance. Following Broennimann *et al.* (2012), the plots of each
320 sampling strategy were then transformed into densities and plotted in the
321 environmental space depicted by the first two PCA axes of the background points.

322

323

324 **3. Results**

325

326 We can examine predefined thresholds in AUC values to have a first overview of
327 the resulted consensus models. We can consider that an SDM is reliable if the
328 evaluation AUC is greater than 0.75 (Pearce and Ferrier, 2000) and the verification
329 AUC is higher than 0.8 (Mateo *et al.*, 2015). Following these criteria (see Appendix
330 C), only for one species the consensus model derived from the systematically sampled
331 data was reliable when the consensus models derived from the opportunistic sample

332 (opportunistic1, opportunistic2, opportunistic3) was not reliable. In contrast,
333 opportunistic sampled data for thirteen species (six for the three opportunistic
334 samplings, six for opportunistic1, one for opportunistic2, and seven for
335 opportunistic3) offered reliable SDMs when the model derived from the systematic
336 sampling did not. We obtained reliable SDMs using the four sampling strategies for
337 six species (i.e., *Quercus pyrenaica*, Fig. 2). For these six species, the comparison
338 between SDMs obtained using the systematic and opportunistic strategies presented
339 the highest Pearson's correlation coefficient values (from 0.61 to 0.88; higher than 0.7
340 for five species). For eight species, no reliable SDMs were obtained for any of the
341 sampling strategies. Three of these species had less than 20 presences (see Appendix
342 C), so the low reliability in this species could be due to small sample size (Wisz *et al.*,
343 2008; Mateo *et al.*, 2010b).

344

345 **Fig. 2.** Pyrenean oak (*Quercus pyrenaica*) distributions models (potential suitability values from 0 to
 346 1000) fitted with the data from the set of sampled plots in each case (black points): a) systematic, b)
 347 opportunistic1, c) opportunistic2, and d) opportunistic3.

348 When the mean AUCs for the different sampling strategies were compared after
 349 removing species effect (Table 1), both opportunistic1 and opportunistic3 models
 350 showed significantly higher accuracy than systematic sampling, whereas
 351 opportunistic2 did not. Thus, the sampling strategies with a larger sample size
 352 ($N_{Opp1}=302$ plots, $N_{Opp3}=177$ plots) resulted on average, on models with a
 353 significantly higher accuracy ($AUC_{Opp1}=0.762$, $AUC_{Opp3}=0.737$). The accuracy was

354 lower for the sampling strategies with smaller sample sizes ($N_{Opp2}=132$ plots,
 355 $N_{Sys}=139$ plots) regardless of the spatial distribution of the plots. No significant
 356 differences were found between systematic and opportunistic plots distribution when
 357 equal sample sizes were compared (p-value = 0.254).

358 Anyway, the averaged AUC increases exclusively related to sample size, though
 359 significant, were low – i.e., Opp1 was 163 plots greater than Opp2 (>120%) and AUC
 360 barely increased 0.04 units (>6%)-. Therefore, the main issue in this comparison of
 361 sampling strategies concerns costs. It is noteworthy that four weeks of work with an
 362 opportunistic sampling strategy slightly outperformed seven weeks of work following
 363 a systematic one (Table 1: Opp1 = 0.0586).

364

Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	DF	t-value	p-value
Intercept (Sys)	0.7036	0.02249	81	31.288	0.000
Opp1	0.0586	0.01632	81	3.590	0.001
Opp2	0.0187	0.01632	81	1.149	0.254
Opp3	0.0331	0.01632	81	2.026	0.046

365

366 **Table 1.** Fixed effects coefficients of the AUC mixed model fitted to evaluate the sampling strategy
 367 influence over models' accuracy after removing species random effect over the error term. Systematic
 368 sampling is stated as the reference group, thus the intercept coefficient matches systematic models'
 369 mean AUC, whereas each of the rest of the coefficients represent the effect of the corresponding
 370 sampling strategy over the mean AUC of systematic sampling group.

371 The four considered sampling strategies captured similarly well the range of
 372 environmental conditions in the study area (Figures 3 and 4), which would contribute
 373 to obtaining reliable SDMs with all the four sampling strategies for the bulk of the
 374 species (unreliable models were obtained only for six species for the four sampling
 375 strategies). This finding is in agreement with the conclusion from the mixed model in

376 Table 1, thus stressing that the major differences in the performance of the SDMs may
377 be due to the sample size in each of the sampling strategies (Mateo *et al.*, 2010b).
378

379

380 **Fig. 3.** Environmental variability measured by a boxplot univariate analysis for six environmental
381 variables (see Material and Methods) used in this study. For each variable the first bar starting from the
382 left represents the background information, the second bar represents the systematic sampling, the third
383 represents the opportunistic1 sampling, the fourth represents the opportunistic2 sampling, and the fifth
384 represents the opportunistic3 sampling.

385

386 **Fig. 4.** Environmental variability measured by the first two PCA axes of a multivariate analysis of the
 387 four sampling strategies employed in this study: systematic, opportunistic1, opportunistic2, and
 388 opportunistic3.

389 The environmental variables with major relative importance to the SDMs were
 390 topographical variables (mainly elevation and slope) and canopy cover (Appendix D).
 391 Hydrography variables (distance to streams) had a relative importance for derived
 392 SDMs for only five plant species; one of them is *Salix atrocinerea*, a species
 393 associated with rivers and streams.

394

395 **4. Discussion**

396

397 *4.1. Sampling strategy and model performance for woody plant species in forest* 398 *landscapes*

399

400 We showed, for the first time, that it is possible to obtain reliable SDMs in forest
401 landscapes with data acquired from an opportunistic low-cost sampling along roads
402 and tracks. These results are coherent with our initial hypotheses. For 20 species out
403 of 28, reliable SDMs were obtained with opportunistic or/and regular-systematic
404 samplings. In these cases, the Pearson's correlation coefficient values were usually
405 high (see Appendix C) when comparing the models generated from the systematic and
406 the opportunistic samplings (only for four species the value was lower than 0.5).
407 This high correlation indicates that the SDMs created with both sampling strategies
408 are comparable, transferable and stable. Both sampling strategies captured
409 environmental variability similarly (Figures 3 and 4), which contributed to obtain
410 comparable and sufficiently reliable SDMs. Therefore, to optimize logistical
411 resources and obtain reliable landscape SDMs, it is crucial to design the sampling
412 strategy as to ensure that the plots cover the full environmental heterogeneity of the
413 study area before their application to forest management strategies, rather than
414 necessarily forcing the plot location to follow a given predefined spatial arrangement
415 (such as that of systematic sampling). We have shown that if opportunistic sampling
416 along roads and tracks allow doing so, which can be evaluated beforehand as shown
417 for our study area, it may be an excellent option that can combine SDMs reliability
418 with reduced inventory costs.

419 It was not possible, however, to construct reliable consensus models for eight of
420 the 28 species (Appendix C). When comparing the models generated from the
421 systematic and the opportunistic samplings, the Pearson's correlation coefficient
422 values were characteristically small (always lower than 0.5, see Appendix C),

423 indicating unstable SDMs. The sample size available for three of these species was
424 low (less than 20 presences), which could be the reason for the unreliable SDMs in
425 these cases (Wisz *et al.*, 2008; Mateo *et al.*, 2010b). The remaining five species
426 (*Calluna vulgaris*, *Cistus laurifolius*, *Erica arborea*, *Thymus mastichina*, and *T. zygis*)
427 show a wide ecological range (López González, 2007). Previous research has shown
428 that widespread species have a tendency to generate less reliable SDMs than narrowly
429 distributed ones (Mateo *et al.*, 2010b; van Proosdij *et al.*, 2016). In addition, at the
430 local scale, other variables (i.e., historical and present forest management, soil and
431 terrain features, etc.) could be needed to model these species accurately.
432 Consequently, these results showed the difficulties in modelling species with a wide
433 ecological range (McPherson and Jetz, 2007; Mateo *et al.*, 2010b). Unlike, for other
434 species (*Fraxinus angustifolia*, *Pinus pinaster*, and *Cytisus scoparius*) we achieved
435 accurate models with small sample sizes and using both sampling strategies. These
436 species are narrowly distributed in the *Sierra del Rincón*. Therefore, fewer plots might
437 be needed to effectively reflect the climatic and the local environmental conditions
438 required for the model training of narrowly distributed species (Mateo *et al.*, 2010b).
439 In this case, we can conclude that the ecology of the species was more significant than
440 the minimum sample size (Mateo *et al.*, 2010b; van Proosdij *et al.*, 2016). However,
441 some of the models derived from low sample size species should be interpreted with
442 caution (Appendix C). The verification AUCs values for these species are close to 1
443 (i.e., excellent models), but when these models are evaluated with independent data
444 (evaluation) AUC is often below 0.75. This is an indication of overfitting and low
445 transferability of the models for these species.

446 Our findings suggest that the relationship between the ecological range of the
447 species and that of the study area is key for determining both the potential accuracy of
448 landscape-scale SDMs and the minimum sample size required to achieve it (van
449 Proosdij *et al.*, 2016). Beyond this fact, if we compare the mean performance of the
450 four sampling strategies leaving aside single species effect (Table 1), the AUC
451 differences between these approaches do not appear to be related to the spatial

452 distribution of the plots (systematic or opportunistic) but to the sampling size. In other
453 words, the spatial configuration of the plots is not fundamental in this case, as none of
454 the sampling designs is environmentally biased. Given a similar fieldwork effort and
455 that both sampling strategies capture similar environmental variability, the
456 opportunistic sampling may outperform in many cases the systematic one due to the
457 smaller sample size of the latter, as it was the case in this study area. Similarly, the
458 same model predictive performance can be obtained with a less demanding fieldwork
459 campaign by using opportunistic sampling, which could help to cover larger study
460 areas and, consequently, to better represent more species.

461

462 *4.2. Implications for forest management*

463

464 Forest management demands unbiased multivariate information on forest species
465 composition and spatial structure (Eskelson *et al.*, 2009). Species distribution models
466 can provide objective potential vegetation and species distribution maps, with
467 innumerable applications in forest management, e.g., selection of species for
468 reforestation or forest restoration (Gastón *et al.*, 2014), adaptation to climate change
469 (Kramer *et al.*, 2010), or control of the spread of invasive species, forest pests and
470 diseases (Václavík *et al.*, 2010; DeRose *et al.*, 2013; Liang *et al.*, 2014). Moreover,
471 SDMs are valuable tools to improve the knowledge of species habitat requirements
472 (Guisan and Thuiller, 2005), which is the basis for many forest management decisions
473 (Lanier, 1994). Although forest ecologists and managers have already accumulated
474 extensive ecological knowledge on main forest tree species (Serrada *et al.*, 2008), the
475 contribution of SDMs to improve management decisions is especially relevant for the
476 rest of plant species. Non-tree plant species have usually received less attention due to
477 their minor economic importance, but they are crucial for maintaining forest
478 biodiversity. For instance, the scrub management, that has received little attention in
479 the past (San Miguel Ayanz *et al.*, 2008), would benefit from a better knowledge on
480 environmental and habitat requirements of shrubs (Bacon, 2003). However, the spatial

481 scale of SDMs is often too coarse for forest management applications, and the
482 development of landscape-level SMDs can be unaffordable in many cases. Therefore,
483 the development of low-cost and accurate SDMs at the landscape scale, like those
484 described here, could foster the application of such models to forest management,
485 ultimately benefiting the efficiency and scope of management decisions.

486 The assessment of biodiversity in National Forest Inventories (NFI), which are
487 usually based on systematic sampling strategies, may also benefit from insights from
488 this study to improve its potential to deliver management-useful SDMs. Biodiversity
489 data in NFIs is often reduced to a short list of species or functional groups (Chirici *et*
490 *al.*, 2011). In such cases, NFI biodiversity data could be complemented with SDMs
491 predictions for more species derived from a much less expensive opportunistic
492 sampling, which could be fit as a relatively inexpensive addition to the fieldwork
493 already conducted for the NFIs as currently designed.

494

495 *4.3. Limitations and future research*

496

497 The advantages of opportunistic sampling along roads and tracks, as opposed to
498 systematic, are expected to be dependent on the density of roads/tracks. In a study
499 area with a high density of roads/tracks, such as the *Sierra del Rincón*, the distance to
500 a road or track will be low in most of the study area, so that no large areas without
501 opportunistic plots will occur. Taking into account the distance between plots of
502 systematic sampling is also important in this regard; if the distance considered is too
503 large, the environmental variability could be underrepresented, or potentially biased,
504 in the sampled plots. In other more remote areas, for example tropical areas, with a
505 much lower density of roads-tracks (Ibisch *et al.*, 2016), the results could change
506 significantly. Future similar research studies should be conducted in other areas with
507 lower road/track density, and with a different set of environmental conditions, to
508 ensure the generality and applicability of our results to other forest landscapes,
509 particularly outside Europe.

510 Because systematic sampling is more resource demanding, future research should
511 emphasize more efficient sampling designs that collect environmental information to
512 get reliable species distribution models at the landscape scale and fine spatial
513 resolution. It could also be interesting to test if the opportunistic sampling strategy
514 may also be extended to other forest attributes different from species occurrences and
515 more related to the traditional practice of silviculture. In this direction, future research
516 could assess the effect of using an opportunistic sampling strategy on the accuracy of
517 typical forest inventory variables such as basal area or standing stock. The
518 opportunistic sampling could be used to complement regular inventories, trying to
519 balance cost and precision in a multipurpose forest inventory. Unfortunately, for some
520 forest inventory variables it is not easy to check in advance if the location of plots
521 along roads and tracks ensures that the heterogeneity of the variable of interest is well
522 covered. Nonetheless, recently and increasingly available products on forest stand
523 structure such as those derived from airborne laser scanner data may help and further
524 extend the research and applied management possibilities in this regard (Næsset,
525 2007).

526 Here, we showed that an opportunistic sampling could help to cover larger study
527 areas and, consequently, to better characterize more species and obtain reliable SDMs.
528 A well-stabilized approach to avoid biased sampling strategies for the construction of
529 SDMs is the use of random-stratified samplings (Hirzel and Guisan, 2002, Dubuis *et*
530 *al.*, 2011), but it can be as resource demanding (in the sampling design and
531 acquisition phases) as a regular strategy. However, future research works could go a
532 step further; a possible new sampling scheme could enable a trade-off between the
533 optimum sampling strategy for SDMs (random-stratified sampling) and cost
534 efficiency (opportunistic sampling along roads and tracks): an environmentally
535 stratified sampling along roads. The random-stratified sampling (Hirzel and Guisan,
536 2002, Dubuis *et al.*, 2011) is based on the stratification of the environmental space
537 (independent variables) to make sure that it is well represented. After that, plots are
538 randomly selected across the strata. But instead of selecting the plots randomly, plots

539 could be selected near the tracks and roads. In this way, it could be possible to sample
540 all the environmental space with lower demand of resources. However, before the
541 application of this sampling strategy, it would be needed to check the availability of
542 roads and tracks in each stratum so that the plots finally represent the full
543 environmental heterogeneity of the study area.

544

545 **5. Conclusions**

546

547 Species distribution models at the landscape scale are powerful tools in forest
548 management, with potential applications in ecological restoration or endangered
549 species management, among others. As far as these models are to be operational for
550 forest managers, one of the most important issues concerns the optimization of the
551 cost of data acquisition. Low-cost sampling strategies should be implemented in
552 practical examples and tested regarding their accuracy. Here, we demonstrated that
553 systematic and opportunistic samplings are both able to generate reliable, fine spatial
554 resolution SDMs for forest plant species at the landscape scale, given that the plots
555 cover the full environmental heterogeneity of the study area. Several species could
556 however not be modelled with the required reliability due to the small sample size or
557 to their broad ecological range.

558 More notably, our results further demonstrate that the larger sample size allowed
559 by opportunistic sampling compensates and outperforms systematic sampling (more
560 resource demanding). This finding suggests that there is potential for a more frequent
561 use of this currently underused opportunistic sampling in forest vegetation
562 inventories, at least as the development of SDMs for woody plant species is
563 concerned. Nevertheless, in our case, the road and track network is remarkably dense
564 compared to other less developed regions with a lower density of transport
565 infrastructures. Therefore, our findings should be interpreted with caution in other
566 forest landscapes, particularly outside Europe. In any case, at the landscape scale, the
567 analysis of the study area before the design and development of the sampling strategy

568 can be much more detailed than at larger scales, which can allow for an efficient
569 selection of the sampling approach and a remarkable saving of resources for forest
570 management planning. It is therefore particularly important to evaluate the potential
571 of different inventory strategies when working at this scale without discarding *a*
572 *priori* options that may be less popular in traditional forest assessments such as
573 sampling opportunistic along tracks.

574

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576

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579 **Supplementary material**

580

581 **Appendix A:** List of modelled species and their abbreviations.

582

583 **Appendix B:** Optimization of low sample size species distribution modelling at
584 landscape scale.

585

586 **Appendix C:** AUC values (verification and evaluation) and sample size for training
587 and validating species distribution models for 28 species (Appendix A), using three
588 different modelling approaches (Appendix B) and four different sampling strategies
589 (regular, opportunistic1, opportunistic2 and opportunistic3). Pearson's correlation
590 coefficient was calculated by comparison of the three opportunistic consensus models
591 with the systematic consensus model only for the second modelling approach.

592

593 **Appendix D:** Relative importance of each independent variable inside the species
594 distribution models. We calculated the mean value (10 replicates models) for each
595 sampling strategy, variable, modelling technique (GLM, BRT, and RF) and species.
596 And finally we calculate the average for each sampling strategy, variable and species.

597

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